

AN EMPIRICAL STUDY ON INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY AND IT ENABLED SERVICES FOR STARTUPS IN INDIA

Dr. S. SEKAR

R L Institute of Management Studies, Madurai, Department of Business Administration, Madurai Kamaraj University.

Dr. M. MUTHUKUMAR

Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, DDE, Madurai Kamaraj University.

Dr. PRAKASH DIVAKARAN

Pro-Vice Chancellor, Himalayan University, Itanagar, Arunachal Pradesh.

Abstract recent

The growth and development of **startups in India** will not happen instantaneously but slowly, over a gradual period. It was since in the year 2008, after a global recession and the introduction of Information Technology hit the world business sector that the new revolution of **startups** began to take shape. The introduction of Information Technology and IT enabled services like Digital Marketing, Digital Sales, Online secure payment, Digital Advertising, Call Centres, Data centres, Hosting Services, and Web Services. etc cover the entire end-to-end operations which exploit information technology and IT Enabled services for supporting and improving the growth and efficiency of startups. Initially, there was misconstrue stating that the introduction of Information Technology and IT Enabled services will cause fewer employment opportunities in startups, but it is not true as it provides enormous amount ideas in leveraging to use new technology services with support startups to increase the business from small scale industry to large and internal business. Therefore, this paper attempts to find out the current scenario and introduction of modern Information Technology (IT) and IT Enabled Services (ITeS) in startups, India and it impacts on business growth.

Keywords: Information Technology (IT), IT Enabled Services (ITeS), Digital Marketing, Data Center, Hosting Services, online secure Services.

INTRODUCTION

A startup or start-up is a firm or company or project initiated by an individual or entrepreneur to seek new ideas effectively and to develop a scalable new business for society. Startup refers to all newly started businesses, including self-employment and businesses that intend to grow beyond single ownership. Most of the time startup may face a huge amount of uncertainty and has high rates of failure, the reason behind this is a lack of planning and confidence to accept failures. Entrepreneurs shall withhold their confidence and look the opportunists in the failure. Some start-ups become unicorns, i.e. privately held startup companies valued at over US\$1 billion. Startup principles include Lean startup, Market validation, Design thinking, Decision-making under uncertainty, partnering, Entrepreneurial learning, and Business Model Design.

Information Technology (IT) was first introduced by Thomas L. Whisler and Harold J. Leavitt in a 1958 article published in the Harvard Business Review. Just 50 years ago,

this term was rarely known, except by those who worked in large organizations, like banks and hospitals that needed to input, process and store data. It is basically the use of computer software and hardware to manage information. A combination of telecommunications and computing for the acquisition, process, storage and dissemination of vocal, pictorial, textual and numeric information.

Information Technology Enabled Services (ITeS) is the internet web-enabled service or electronic or Tele-working service which exploits to use of computer software, hardware, and technology to ensure confidentiality, Integrity, availability, security, authenticity and non-reputation in the business transaction. IT is used to maintain the governance, quality of service (QOS) as well as efficiency of an organization.

Telemarketing, Helpdesk, customer service centres, Data warehouse, Data Mining, and Transcription centres are some of the important areas where the IT-enabled services are mostly used. India now dominates the global market for offshoring IT-enabled services.

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY (IT)

Based on the storage and processing technologies employed, it is possible to distinguish four distinct phases of IT development: pre-mechanical (3000 BC – 1450 AD), mechanical (1450–1840), electromechanical (1840–1940), and electronic (1940–present). This article focuses on the most recent period (electronic).

Pre - Mechanical	Mechanical	Electromechanical	Electronic
Between 3000BC and 1450 AD	Between 1450 and 1840	Between 1840 and 1940	Between 1940 and 2020
- Alphabet	-Pasaline	-Telecommunication	- Vaccum tubes
- Petroglyph	-Slide rule	-Telegraph	-Transistors
- Abacus	-Different Engine	-Telephone	-IC,LSI,VLSI,SUPER COMPUTER

Information technology (IT) is the use of computers to store, retrieve, transmit, and manipulate data or information. IT is typically used within the context of business operations as opposed to personal or entertainment technologies. IT is considered to be a subset of information and communication technology (ICT). ICT includes any communication device or application encompassing Telephone, Radio, Television, Cellular phone, Computers, Networks, Satellite Systems, Hardware and Software. An **information technology system (IT system)** is generally an information system, a communications system or, more specifically speaking, a computer system – including all hardware, software and peripheral equipment – operated by a limited group of users.

Humans have been storing, retrieving, manipulating, and communicating information since the Sumerians in Mesopotamia developed writing in about 3000 BC, but the term information technology in its modern sense first appeared in a 1958 article published in the Harvard Business Review; authors Harold J. Leavitt and Thomas L. Whisler commented that "the new technology does not have a single established name. Yet the term is commonly used as a synonym for computers and computer networks, but it also encompasses other information distribution technologies such as television and telephones. Several products or services within

an economy are associated with information technology, including computer hardware, software, electronics, semiconductors, internet, telecom equipment, and e-commerce.

IT-enabled Services (ITeS) includes any communication device or application or service functions under the network or internet connectivity. ITeS stands for Information Technology Enabled Services. It includes a wide variety of operation functions, which uses information technology to improve the efficiency of an organization. Most of the major companies in the world prefer to India for outsourcing IT Enable Services (ITES).

India's 20 Best Small & Startup ITeS Companies

Xactly Corporation xactlycorp.com	Yodlee Infotech yodlee.com	Livestream Technologies new.livestream.com	Esko esko.com
Sanovi sanovi.com	Aryaka Networks aryaka.com	Allstate Solutions allstate.com	Amysoft Technologies amysoft.com
Data Patterns datapatternsindia.com	Divum divum.in	Dot Com Infoway dotcominfoway.com	Embytes embytes.com
Stoke stoke.com	Talisma talisma.com	The Digital Group thedigitalgroup.com	Toboc toboc.com
Trigent Software trigent.com	Velankani Software velankani.com	Vmoksha vmokshagroup.com	Xora xora.com

IT enabled Service: The Revenue Matrix

Benefits of using IT Enable Service in Startup Companies

Simple Process	Financial Benefits from Government	Income Tax reduction	Registration Benefits
Government Tenders	Huge Networking Opportunities	R & D Facilities	Online Access
24 x 7 Services	Investor Option	Business Efficiency	Governance
Employment opportunities	App-enabled support	Increase productivity	Profit Maximization
Technology Driven	Competitive	Dynamic in nature	Sustainability

CONCLUSION

In the present scenario, running the startups business or services with the entire available infrastructure is not the key to success. Convergence Information Technology environment is necessary and modern IT-Enabled tool or application presents are required which make the startup owner or Users forget all worries in doing startup online business. Thus, Information Technology and IT enables Services plays a vital role in Startup Business. New and innovative aspects of IT and ITeS can be added to keep up the consumer's delight.

REFERENCES

1. Information Technology in Business Management R. (2015). Dr.Mukesh Dhunna and J.B. Dixit. University Science Press.
2. Development of Entrepreneurship R (2004). G.S Batra,Deep & Deep Publications Pvt Ltd.
3. Pradhan, S. (2004). Retailing Management. Tata McGrew-Hill.
4. Rampal, M. K., & Gupta, S. L. (2000). Services Marketing. Galgotia.
5. Lovelock, C., & Wirtz. J. (2010). Services Marketing: People, Technology, Strategy. Prentice Hall.
6. Entrepreneurship Development, R (2011). S L Gupta, Arun Mittal, International Book House Pvt. Limited. .